

A Modified LEACH Routing Protocol in Terms of Lifetime Enhancement Schema Comparative to PEGASIS Protocol in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs)

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Abstract

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is a dominant technology among different wireless communication technologies. It's very important to maximize the lifetime of networks for better and long-term performance. However, the lifetime of a network depends greatly on the lifetime of the battery of related nodes. Generally, Sensor networks are limited in energy and, thus, require the use of routing protocols to minimize energy consumption. After a comparative study of the performance of two hierarchical routing protocols namely LEACH and PEGASIS, which indicates that PEGASIS has a longer lifetime than LEACH because of its low energy consumption techniques but has more delay, this paper presents a lifetime enhancement schema and a modified version of LEACH protocol to overcome the short lifetime problem of LEACH protocol comparative to PEGASIS protocol. The modified LEACH protocol increases the lifetime of the network by 300% more than that of the traditional LEACH protocol.

Keywords: WSNs, Routing Protocols, LEACH, PEGASIS, Modified LEACH.

1. Introduction

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is one of the most important and widely used technologies in twenty-first-century consist of a large number of low-cost, low-power, and multifunctional wireless sensor nodes that have capabilities of sensing and collecting data, establishing wireless communication between different nodes and performing various computational and data processing operations. Sensor nodes are deployed into a particular area to perform a certain task of sensing or tracking and returning the captured data to a base station [1]. A sensor node is a small device which has a micro-sensor technology, low power signal processing and computational logic, and a short-range communication capability. A typical sensor node consists of four basic components: sensing unit, processing unit, transceiver unit and power unit [2]. WSNs are used in many applications such as environment monitoring, military surveillance, and industrial process control [3]. The use of wireless sensor networks is increasing day by day but is limited by the battery life of the sensor nodes and the recharging of sensor nodes is usually impractical. Therefore, limited energy is an essential design issue in wireless sensor networks. In the case of sensor networks, the focus of the network protocols is on low power consumption to increase the lifetime of the network. The efficiency of the wireless sensor network largely depends on the routing protocol used. There are various problems in wireless sensor networks such as area coverage, position estimation, etc. Besides, the major problems of WSNs are energy consumption and lifetime. In Wireless sensor networks, most of the energy is consumed in transmission and receiving data as compared to sensing and processing. The efficient utilization of energy sources in a sensor node is very important criteria to prolong the lifetime of a wireless sensor network. Increasing the lifetime of the network is very important in WSNs. Wireless sensor networks have been explored to many protocols specifically designed for sensor networks in which energy consideration was very crucial. Lifetime will be increased when energy consumption will be decreased and thus, the network protocol should take care of issues like energy-efficiency, system

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lifetime and delay. There are various routing protocols and selecting an energy-efficient routing protocol is very important for WSNS to overcome energy consumption and lifetime problem [4].

The major contribution of this paper is the proposal of a new modified LEACH protocol that will increase the lifetime of a network system by 300% more than traditional LEACH protocol focusing on residual energy of the node.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives the basic knowledge of LEACH and PEGASIS routing protocol. Performance evaluation of LEACH and PEGASIS is explained in Section 3 and lifetime enhancement schema is explained in Section 4. Section 5 proposes and discusses a modified LEACH protocol and Section 6 concludes this paper.

2. Overview of LEACH and PEGASIS Routing Protocol

In WSN, routing protocols determine how different nodes communicate with each other to distribute the information through the network. The main reason behind the use of routing protocol is to ensure the successful transition of the packets from the source node to the sink or base station (BS). LEACH and PEGASIS are examples of hierarchical routing protocols.

A secure routing protocol should guarantee the Confidentiality, Integrity, Authenticity, and Availability. In this section hierarchical routing protocols namely LEACH and PEGASIS are described in detail.

2.1 LEACH (Low Energy Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy) Protocol

LEACH is a hierarchical and cluster-based routing protocol in which a cluster head is selected to maintain the routing procedure. A network is divided into some clusters and each cluster has one cluster head. Cluster head performs the following task:

- Collects data from the sensor nodes.
- Sends the collected data to the sink node after the data aggregation process.
- Creates a TDMA-based schedule where each node is assigned a time-slot used for data transmission [5].

Each cluster chooses a number between 0 and 1 and this number is compared with a threshold value, $T(n)$, of a node. The cluster head is selected using this threshold value [6]. If the selected value is less than the threshold value, then the node becomes the cluster head, else it behaves as an ordinary node [7] [8]. Each node becomes a cluster head for a single round. The threshold value is given by the Eq. (1).

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \notin G \\ \frac{P}{1 - P(r \bmod (1/P))} & \forall n \in G \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, p is the desired percentage of cluster heads (e.g. 0.05), r is the current round and G is the set of nodes that have not been cluster heads in the last $1/p$ rounds [8]. LEACH is completely a distributed network that requires no control information from the base station and no node requires the knowledge of the global network. The LEACH protocol is consists of two phases: Set-up phase and Steady phase.

Set-up phase has three fundamental steps:

- Cluster head advertisement.
- Cluster set up.

- Creation of transmission schedule.

Steady-state phase focuses on:

- Data collection.
- Data Aggregation and
- Delivery of the collected data to the base station.

There are three types of communications in the clustering mechanism: inter-cluster communication (cluster to clusters communication), intra-cluster communication (communication within a cluster), cluster-based communication (communication between CH and BS). Inter and intra-cluster communication require less amplification energy compared to cluster-based communication. Therefore, by keeping different amplification energy levels for inter and intra-cluster communication with respect to cluster-based communication type, the lifetime of sensor nodes can be improved [9].

2.2 PEGASIS (Power-Efficient Gathering in Sensor Information System) Protocol

PEGASIS protocol is also a hierarchical protocol that follows the chain-based approach and the greedy algorithm. The sensor nodes either organize themselves to form the chain or they use a greedy approach. If any of the nodes dies in between, then the chain is reconstructed to bypass the dead node. One chain-leader is selected for the chain. The chain-leader node will transmit the data to the base station (BS) [10]. The main goal of PEGASIS is to receive and transmit data to and from the nearest neighbor and take turns being the leader for transmission to the BS. Gathered data moves from node to node, get fused and eventually, a designated node transmits to the base station. Chain-leader is selected randomly. All the data is collected to the leader node, get fused and send it to the base station. PEGASIS performs data fusion at every node except the end nodes in the chain. Each node will fuse it's neighbor's data with its own to generate a single packet of the same length and then transmit that to another neighbor [11].

3. Comparative Analysis of LEACH and PEGASIS Routing Protocol

3.1 Simulation Environment

MATLAB is used to simulate and analyze the performance of both LEACH and PEGASIS protocols. MATLAB is an interactive system whose basic data element is an array and it does not require dimensioning. It allows users to solve various technical and computing problems with matrix and vector formulations.

3.2 Simulation Parameters

In the simulation process, the following network parameters have been used:

Table 1 Simulation Parameters

Parameters	Value
Simulation area (m)	100 x 100
Initial energy	0.25 j
Number of nodes	50/100/150/200
Energy transmission (j)	$50 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Energy reception (j)	$50 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Simulator	MATLAB
Rounds	4000

3.3 Simulation Result and Performance Analysis

Lifetime Analysis: The network lifetime is the number of rounds that can be determined as the start of the operation to the round that the last node dies. Network lifetime is divided into stability and instability period. The stability period is the number of the rounds started from the beginning of the operation until the first node of the network is dead. Where the instability period is the number of rounds when the first node dies in the network to the death of the last node in the network.

Fig. 1 The lifetime of LEACH and PEGASIS protocols

The lifetime of both LEACH and PEGASIS protocols is given by Fig. 1. Where Fig.1 (a) shows the lifetime of both LEACH and PEGASIS using 50 nodes. The first node in the LEACH protocol dies at round 95, whereas the first node dies at round 226 in PEGASIS. This study shows that the PEGASIS protocol has a long stable period than the LEACH protocol and both LEACH and PEGASIS protocols have a network lifetime of 196 and 391 rounds respectively. This indicates that the lifetime of PEGASIS protocol is better than that of LEACH protocol. Fig.1 (b) shows the simulation result of the lifetime of LEACH and PEGASIS protocols for 100 nodes. Similarly Fig.1 (c) and Fig.1 (d) show the lifetime of LEACH and PEGASIS protocol for 150 and 200 nodes. The simulation result of the lifetime of both protocols using different numbers of nodes is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Lifetime of LEACH and PEGASIS Protocols

Protocol	50 Nodes	100 Nodes	150 Nodes	200 Nodes
LEACH	196 rounds	253 rounds	261 rounds	321 rounds
PEGASIS	391 rounds	455 rounds	501 rounds	521 rounds

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Energy Consumption: In WSNs, if a node dies, the network loses control over the space, which was being sensed by that dead node. The death of that node creates a hole in the sensing field and the network will be incomplete. To avoid such situations, a network should monitor the energy consumption of each node. Energy consumption is an important issue for the longevity of the network and a node should not be consumed energy at such a rate that may harm the network. Fig. 2 shows the energy consumption of LEACH and PEGASIS protocols for 50, 100, 150 and 200 nodes. These indicate that the energy consumption of the LEACH protocol is much more than the PEGASIS protocol.

(a) 50 Nodes

(b) 100 Nodes

(c) 150 Nodes

(d) 200 Nodes

Fig. 2 Energy consumption of LEACH and PEGASIS protocols

Delay: PEGASIS forms a single chain among the nodes. So it introduces excessive delay. But LEACH introduces less delay than PEGASIS. LEACH performs better than PEGASIS in terms of delay.

In this simulation, the merits and demerits of LEACH and PEGASIS protocols have been observed concerning network lifetime, stable period, energy consumption, and delay. Lifetime and energy efficiency are the most important parameters for a wireless network. The simulation results show that PEGASIS outperforms LEACH by minimizing the distance between non-leader nodes, limiting the number of transmission and reception of data among different nodes, and using only one transmission to the BS per round. However, PEGASIS introduces an excessive delay in transmission since it needs to form a chain among the sensors. LEACH outperforms PEGASIS by reducing the delay. LEACH has less network lifetime than PEGASIS. Lifetime enhancement schema and a modified version of LEACH protocol are proposed to increase the lifetime of LEACH protocol.

4. Proposed Lifetime Enhancement Schema of LEACH Protocol

In WSN data should reach the destination through the intermediate nodes. If the distance between intermediate sensor nodes and the sink is long, more energy is consumed. LEACH protocol has less network lifetime than PEGASIS. In this section, an enhancement schema is proposed to improve the lifetime of LEACH. Therefore, by reducing the distance between sensor nodes and sink, it is possible to increase the network lifetime of LEACH. The distance between sensor nodes and BS can be reduced by increasing the number of nodes in a particular area. When the number of nodes is increased, the distance will be reduced and will consume less energy for intra and inter-communication routing protocol.

The simulation of the LEACH protocol at 0.05 probability is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. In LEACH, all nodes have the same energy (0.25 j). The network lifetime and energy consumption of LEACH protocol are simulated for 50, 100, 150 and 200 nodes. Fig. 3 shows the graphical representation of the result of the network lifetime of LEACH protocol that indicates that the lifetime increases if the number of nodes increases and Fig. 4 shows the energy consumption of LEACH protocol at 0.05 probability.

Fig. 3 Lifetime of LEACH protocol at 0.05 probability

Fig. 4 Energy consumption of LEACH protocol at 0.05 probability

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Though this enhancement schema increases the lifetime of the network, it increases energy consumption as well. This requires to overcome the energy consumption problem for a better network lifetime. Considering the energy consumption problem, a modified LEACH protocol is proposed.

5. Proposed Modified LEACH Protocol

A new modified LEACH protocol is proposed to increase the lifetime of the LEACH protocol by considering the residual energy means the current energy of the node that reduces the energy consumption of the network. Residual energy affects the lifetime of wireless sensor networks. This energy considered during clustering and routing approached to maximize the network lifetime. To prolong the network lifetime, an efficient power control mechanism is used to reduce the power consumption in sensor nodes. In traditional LEACH protocol, the cluster head selection process depends on random probability, residual energy or current energy of node is not considered. A node will be cluster head if a random number generated by a node satisfies the following condition given by Eq. (2), discussed in LEACH protocol in section 2:

$$\text{If } (\text{rand} \leq (p / (1 - p * \text{mod}(r, \text{round}(1/p)))))) \quad (2)$$

In our modified LEACH, the current node energy is considered and multiplied with the previous value used for cluster head selection in traditional LEACH protocol. Cluster head needs more energy than non-cluster head nodes. In the modified LEACH protocol, a node will be cluster head, which satisfies the condition given by Eq. (3).

$$\text{If } (\text{rand} \leq (p / (1 - p * \text{mod}(r, \text{round}(1/p)))) * \text{current energy of the node} / \text{total energy of the network}) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5 Lifetime of LEACH protocol and modified LEACH protocol

Fig. 5 shows the comparison of the lifetime of modified LEACH and traditional LEACH protocol. The figure shows that the modified LEACH has a higher lifetime than the traditional LEACH protocol. The stable period of LEACH is at 365 round, whereas the stable period of modified LEACH is at 1131 round. The longer the stable period is, the better the performance of the network. Therefore, with a longer stable period, the Modified LEACH protocol gives a 300% increased lifetime than the traditional LEACH protocol.

5.1 Comparative Analysis of LEACH and Modified LEACH Protocol

A modified LEACH protocol is proposed to increase the network's lifetime. In the modified LEACH protocol, to select a node as a cluster head, the current energy of that node is considered. Cluster head needs more energy

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than a normal node to collect data from cluster members and then aggregate and transmit the collected data to the base station. Network lifetime is defined as the time from the beginning of the simulation to the time when the last node died. Fig. 6 shows a comparative analysis of LEACH and modified LEACH protocol according to the lifetime of the network. It gives the percentage of the dead nodes in different rounds. In LEACH, 80% nodes die at 656 round, but in modified LEACH, 80% nodes die at 3675 round, which indicates a 300% improvement in the lifetime of the network. In modified LEACH, residual energy is considered to increase the lifetime of the network with reduced energy consumption.

Fig. 6 Comparative analysis of LEACH and modified LEACH protocols

4. Conclusions

Wireless sensor network operates with the limited capacity of batteries and this energy limitation affects the overall performance of the network. The main challenges in designing a protocol for wireless sensor network is the consideration of the lifetime and energy efficiency due to the limited energy of the sensor nodes. The main purpose of using any routing protocol is to make the network as energy-efficient as possible to keep it running for a longer period. This paper presented the comparative study of LEACH and PEGASIS routing protocols describing the working process of these two routing protocols. The working process of these two protocols is simulated using MATLAB and the comparative study of the performance of these protocols is done based on the outcome of lifetime, energy consumption of the network and delays in transmission related to each protocol. The simulation shows that the PEGASIS protocol has a higher lifetime than LEACH protocol and even consumes less energy than LEACH protocol. However, in the LEACH protocol, the transmission delay is much lesser than the PEGASIS protocol which is a great characteristic of any network.

The main purpose of the work presented in this paper is to increase the lifetime of LEACH protocol maintaining a low transmission delay of the network and improving lifetime requires minimizing the energy consumption of the network. A lifetime enhancement schema is used to increase the lifetime of the network increasing the numbered nodes used. This increased number of nodes increases the lifetime of the network by reducing the distance between different nodes. However, it increases energy consumption as well, as more nodes consume more power. A modified LEACH protocol is proposed to increase the lifetime of LEACH protocol overcoming different limitations related to power consumption. In the proposed protocol, the cluster head selection process of LEACH protocol is modified by including the residual energy that the traditional LEACH protocol does not consider. The proposed protocol, the modified LEACH protocol, increases the lifetime of the network by

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reducing the energy consumption and gives 300% better performance than the traditional LEACH protocol in terms of lifetime.

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